

Quantum Mechanics, Equilibrium and Freezing Out Time

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Equilibrium in classical statistical mechanics (e.g. a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas) is often associated with a freezing out of time, i.e. a kind of steady state picture. Many particles exist and they move in all directions with various momenta and collide. In quantum mechanics, one often has a single particle and so such a picture or a notion of freezing out time seems unusual. In particular, no such equilibrium ideas are applied to classical mechanics, for which one also has a particle moving in one direction. We suggest that if one consider the idea of dynamics in terms of a "running movie" associated with a kind of time probability $P_1(t)$ and a kind of spatial probability $P_2(x)$, then running the moving backwards may be described by $P_1(-t)$ and $P_2(-x)$. To obtain a steady state condition, one may try to freeze out time and motion in space, i.e. demand that $P_1(t)P_1(-t) = \text{constant}$ and $P_2(x)P_2(-x) = \text{constant}$. Taking d/dt of the first expression and d/dx of the second leads to a form which suggests a possible solution for $P_1(t)$ being an eigenfunction of d/dt and $P_2(x)$, of d/dx . These solutions become complex if one wishes to have a kind of variance in t and x . This line of argument seems to be based on a steady state picture and we argue that the description of a quantum bound state is also very much a steady state scenario with localized probability within classical turning points, but also tunnelling in and out. In other words, a steady stream solution requires both, except in the case of a infinite well.

One feature of the freezing out of time is that it allows for a solution of both $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. x and t are treated on an equal footing, as in special relativity. In fact, we make a link to special relativity by using E (energy) as the time eigenvalue and p as the spatial one.. In previous notes, $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ made use of the directional feature of momentum which does not carry over to energy, E .

Classical Statistical Equilibrium

A feature of classical statistical equilibrium (although not a formal requirement) is that one has a static or steady state picture with time frozen out, as in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. Each gas particle may have momentum in a particular direction and exist at a point in space, but overall the system may be described in terms of probabilities, as in the case of a gas with a potential $V(x)$, i.e.

$$\text{Probability}(x,p) = C \exp(-pp/2mT - V(x)/T). \quad ((1))$$

Classical mechanics, on the other hand, does not freeze out time, it does the opposite. It follows a particle in time. Thus, an equilibrium picture is usually not associated with classical mechanics, but rather a dynamic one. In particular, one has a single particle and so there is no averaging out of properties of many particles.

Quantum Mechanics and the Freezing Out of Time

Even though a single particle may be moving in one direction (which does not imply a freezing out of time), one may view this as a "running of a movie" and consider running the movie backwards. If one introduces a "kind of probability" function in time, $P_1(t)$, and another in space, $P_2(x)$, then to freeze out time for a single particle moving in one direction, one may impose:

$$P_1(-t)P_1(t) = \text{constant} \quad ((2A)) \quad P_2(x)P_2(-x) = \text{constant} \quad ((2B))$$

Changing t to $-t$ reorders ascending values in the opposite manner as does changing x to $-x$. In other words, $x=3$ is greater than $x=2$, while $x=-2$ is greater than $x=-3$, so if one moves in ascending order, one moves from -2 to -3 , i.e. in the opposite order of 2 to 3 .

An important feature of the above is that it immediately puts t and x on a similar footing. (In previous notes, we considered the spatial part alone and focused on motion in one direction and another, i.e. the vector behaviour of p (momentum). Here this is not done. Treating t and x on the same footing is reminiscent of special relativity and, in fact, special relativity will be used in our argument.

First, however, we suggest taking d/dt of ((2A)) and d/dx of ((2B)):

$$P1(-t) dP1(t)/dt + P1(t) dP1(-t)/dt = 0 \quad ((3A)) \text{ and } P2(-x)dP2(x)/dx + P2(x)dP2(-x)/dx \quad ((3B))$$

An immediate solution is obtained if $P1(x)$ is an eigenfunction of d/dt and $P2(x)$, of d/dx with $P1(-t)$ and $P2(-x)$ yielding minus the eigenvalue of the positive case. The question is: What eigenvalues should be used?

Given the link with special relativity, suggested above, we consider E as an eigenvalue for t and p for x . If one wishes $P1(t)$ and $P2(x)$ to be somewhat invariant in t and x , i.e. not grow or shrink, then:

$$i d/dt P1(t) = E P1(t) \text{ or } P1(t) = \exp(-iEt) \quad ((4A)) \text{ and } -i d/dx P2(x) = p P2(x) \text{ or } P2(x) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((4B))$$

In other words, in form, the t and x solutions are very much the same as both follow from the freezing out of time through running a movie forwards and backwards and arguing that the product of probabilities eliminates changes in t and x . In other words, an equilibrium type of argument may be applied to unidirectional motion to obtain a probabilistic solution linked with a steady state type of picture. We suggest that this interpretation must be kept in mind when solving problems, especially the single particle bound state one.

Consequences of the Freezing Out of Time

An immediate consequence of the above ideas is that:

$$P1(-t, E1) P2(t, E2) \text{ is not a constant } ((5A)) \text{ and } P2(-x, p1) P2(x, p2) \text{ is not a constant } ((5B))$$

In other words, mixing "kind of probabilities" for $E1, E2$ and $p1, p2$ does not lead to a constant. As a result, it may be good to consider the meaning of the constant in ((2A)) and ((2B)) in the first place. The physical scenario is one of a particle which moves in one direction, as in classical mechanics. The constant implies a freezing out of time, i.e. a removal of motion in all x, t . This leads to "kind of probabilities" $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ which have modulus 1, i.e. the modulus squared treats all t points as the same and all x points as the same. The product values (i.e. modulus squared) ((2A)) and ((2B)) thus represent $P(t)$ and $P(x)$ in the sense of the probability P describing the weight assigned to each t and x point. In the case of ((5A)) and ((5B)) not equaling a constant, one may suggest that the weights $P(t)$ and $P(x)$ vary in t and x . This is the quantum feature of interference. Thus, we suggest using the modulus squared as a recipe for finding the weights associated with t and x .

Interference

In the above section, we suggested ((5A)) and ((5B)) lead to nonconstant values. How is this linked to freezing out of time? We consider a two slit problem and use $\exp(ipx)$ as a "kind of probability". If the slits are close (of the order of \hbar/p), one may suggest there is a probability for the particle to interact with each, as the probabilistic approach does not follow the particle at exact x points in time. Maximum entropy suggests assigning equal weights to each slit (i.e. no bias). There is then a probability for the quantum particle to pass through one slit or the other, i.e. an OR "kind

of probability" situation:

$\exp(i p_1 \cdot x) + \exp(i p_2 \cdot x)$ ((6)) where p_1 and p_2 have the same magnitude, but different directions

If one wishes to create a steady state or time frozen picture for ((6)), then one may multiply ((6)) by its complex conjugate and one may see that interference shifts weights in space so that one does have the simple constant value of ((2B)).

Implications of the Steady State, Frozen Time Picture

The scenario used above deals with frozen time by considering probabilities for motion in a movie and for motion in the movie running backwards. This was associated with d/dt for energy and d/dx for momentum. If one considers a steady state picture, i.e. an equilibrium picture, then one does not have sharp positions of the particle, but rather a wavelength situation. This, together with d/dx , leads to a probability for all x , even for a bound state. In classical physics, the bound particle only exists within the classical turning. A consequence of the movie running forwards and backwards is that one may a particle tunnelling out or into the bound region, which is much more of an equilibrium type of picture for no infinite potential walls, then the classical motion of a particle bouncing back and forth.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we seek an equilibrium type description of a particle moving in one direction, which is normally considered a classical mechanical problem. We suggest that freezing out time is a key feature and consider "kind of probability" functions $P_1(t)$ and $P_2(x)$ such that $P_1(-t)P_1(t) = \text{constant}$ and $P_2(x)P_2(-x) = \text{constant}$. This places x and t on the same footing (as in special relativity). In other words, using $P_1(t)$ for a movie running forwards and $P_1(-t)$ for it running backwards, we suggest that the product (an AND situation in probability) freezes out motion, with a similar result holding for $P_2(x)$. In previous notes, we only considered $P_2(x)$ and focused on the vector nature of p to obtain p and $-p$. Here that is not done.

Taking d/dt and d/dx of these product = constant expressions leads to expressions which have eigenvalues of d/dt and d/dx as solutions if $d/dt P_1(+/- t) = +/- \text{eigenvalue } P_1(+/- t)$ and a similar expression for $P_2(x)$. We suggest that given the equal treatment of t and x here, one associate this approach with special relativity and use E and p as the eigenvalues. This leads to $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ solutions, if one does not want the solution to grow or shrink indefinitely. We suggest that the constant value, obtained by freezing out time, also represents $P(t)$ or $P(x)$, i.e. the probability weight associated with t or x . In other words, one directional motion at constant speed ensures an equal weight for each t and for each x as well. Thus, we use the $P_1(-t)P_1(t)$ or $P_2(-x)P_2(x)$ recipe to calculate probability weights for t and x . We apply these ideas to the two slit interference example, to show that in such a case, one no longer has a constant when one tries to freeze out x , but rather a periodic pattern in x .

Finally, we consider a single particle bound case and argue that the steady state/time freeze picture considers probability in all of space (except in the infinite well situation) and so includes tunnelling in and out of bound area.